

Network Effects and Agreement Drift in LLM Debates

Erica Cau^{1,2*}

Andrea Failla^{1,2†}

Giulio Rossetti^{2‡}

Abstract

Large Language Models (LLMs) have demonstrated an unprecedented ability to simulate human-like social behaviors, making them useful tools for simulating complex social systems. However, it remains unclear to what extent these simulations can be trusted to accurately capture key social mechanisms, particularly in highly unbalanced contexts involving minority groups. This paper uses a network generation model with controlled homophily and class sizes to examine how LLM agents behave collectively in multi-round debates. We show that LLM agents exhibit convergence and polarization patterns that are highly sensitive to network structure and relative group sizes. Moreover, our findings highlight a particular directional susceptibility that we term *agreement drift*, in which agents are more likely to shift toward specific positions on the opinion scale. Overall, our findings highlight the need to disentangle structural effects from model biases before treating LLM populations as behavioral proxies for human groups.

Keywords: LLM ; Opinion Dynamics ; Homophily ; Social Simulation

1 Introduction

The introduction of Large Language Models (LLMs) [1–4] has revolutionized the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP), advancing the ability of language models to solve text-related tasks and generate texts that closely resemble human ones [5]. These models have demonstrated remarkable proficiency across a broad spectrum of NLP tasks [6–8], marking a transition in the development of general-purpose AI models and progress toward artificial general intelligence (AGI) [9]. In addition to their technical capabilities, LLMs have demonstrated an unprecedented ability to simulate human social behaviors. When prompted correctly, LLMs demonstrated the ability to mimic *user personae* with specific demographic and psychological traits [10–12], occupation [13, 14], political leanings [14–16], and, in general, human behavior [17], making them valuable tools for studying their potential behavior when interacting in complex simulated societies [13, 18, 19]. As these models become increasingly widespread across various applications, comprehending their collective behavior becomes essential.

A key question is whether LLMs can spontaneously exhibit human-like social behaviors as emergent properties [20] arising from their training processes, rather than through explicit behavioral programming. For instance, LLMs have demonstrated the ability to exhibit simulated Theory of Mind [21], which might enable subjective behavioral modeling and the comprehension of ambiguous natural language instructions [22]. There has been considerable debate, with studies offering contradictory evidence [23–28]. However, even a simulated Theory of Mind could help LLMs interact more naturally with other agents.

Such collective behaviors, while useful for better understanding LLMs and human behavior, may introduce previously unknown biases into decision-making processes or exacerbate societal biases embedded in training data, with potentially unknown effects on human-LLM interactions [19]. While much of the literature has focused on defining unstructured agent interactions, such as discussions on controversial topics like climate

*Affiliations: 1 Department of Computer Science, University of Pisa; 2 ISTI-CNR. ORCID: 0009-0005-7267-9870. Email: erica.cau@phd.unipi.it.

†Corresponding author. Affiliations: 1 Department of Computer Science, University of Pisa; 2 ISTI-CNR. ORCID: 0009-0009-6162-0274. Email: andrea.failla@phd.unipi.it. Website: <https://andreafailla.github.io>.

‡Affiliation: 2 ISTI-CNR. ORCID: 0000-0003-3373-1240. Email: giulio.rossetti@isti.cnr.it. Website: <https://giuliorossetti.net>.

change [15, 29] or genetically modified food [12], less attention has been given to investigating more structured populations of agents. When we interact with others, we form social ties that can be modelled as edges in a graph, with individuals acting as nodes. Human societies are grounded in unwritten social rules, such as homophily, exemplified by the saying *birds of a feather flock together* [30]. People tend to gravitate toward those perceived as similar, thereby strengthening their connections with them, while avoiding those perceived as too different. This behavior has various consequences: it might amplify social divisions, strengthen boundaries between groups, and eventually lead to the segregation of populations into homogeneous clusters.

Why are these matters important? There are at least two reasons why these questions need to be addressed. By observing how LLM agents respond to topological factors such as homophily and class imbalance, it is possible to characterize the latent predispositions that emerge from their collective behavior. Understanding these dynamics is essential if we are to interpret their outputs reliably, especially in high-stakes or decision-critical contexts. Second, since LLMs are increasingly employed in agent-based simulations of human social systems [18, 31, 32], it is crucial to evaluate the extent to which their interactions accurately reflect real human behavior. Many recent works position LLMs as *proxies for human behavior* [33], especially in fields where language is pivotal, such as psychology. However, such usage assumes a degree of behavioral realism that may not hold under closer scrutiny [34]. If LLM populations diverge systematically from known patterns in human opinion formation — e.g., by converging too quickly, suppressing disagreement, or exhibiting exaggerated sensitivity to class size — this raises questions about their validity as tools for modeling human collective behavior. Thus, understanding when and how LLMs approximate or deviate from human-like dynamics is critical for both methodological validity and ethical use.

Our contribution. This study aims to bridge the gaps outlined above by examining how the degree of homophily and relative class sizes within the interaction network affect opinion evolution in LLM societies. Previous work has investigated the homophilic mechanism in networks generated by LLM agents, focusing particularly on how the attributes of LLM agents (e.g., gender, age, or political leaning) influence link formation, leading to assortative structures and clustered communities [35]. In contrast, we model populations of LLMs as agents within a preferential attachment framework augmented with homophilic edge formation [36]. This allows us to manipulate not only traditional network parameters (e.g., degree distribution) but also the social alignment of nodes (via homophily) and the distribution of opinions (via class size imbalance). We simulate debates among agents on a given initial statement and trace how opinions evolve over time. Our investigation is structured around the following research questions:

RQ1. *How does homophily influence opinion dynamics in balanced LLM agent populations?* In this experiment, the agent population is evenly divided (50-50) between two opinion classes. We vary the homophily parameter while keeping all other factors constant, particularly class size, to isolate and observe the impact of homophilic attachment on the trajectory and convergence of opinion evolution.

RQ2. *How does the effect of homophily on LLM opinion dynamics change under increasingly imbalanced class distributions?* Building on RQ1, we investigate how skewing the initial class size distribution (i.e., from 70-30 to 90-10) affects the role of homophily in opinion dynamics. This allows us to examine whether the presence of a minority affects the extent to which homophily influences consensus formation and opinion stability.

RQ3. *How do the initial stances of minority and majority groups influence opinion dynamics?* We compare scenarios in which (i) the majority agrees with the initial statement while the minority disagrees, and (ii) the minority agrees with the initial statement while the majority disagrees. Given the LLMs’ tendency toward agreement [37, 38], this question probes whether aligning with the majority on a particular stance amplifies or mitigates its influence on final opinion distributions.

RQ4. *How does knowledge of neighbors’ opinion distribution affect opinion dynamics?* We explore scenarios in which agents have information about their neighbors’ opinion distributions and assess the impact of this knowledge on opinion evolution.

Coherently with previous research, we find that LLM populations exhibit a systematic directional bias

Figure 1: **Graphical schema of the LLM-OD framework.** The LLM agents population is initialized as nodes in a network; each agent is an LLM instance with an initial opinion in the range $[0, 6]$ (a). At each iteration, two neighbor agents are chosen and prompted to act as *Opponent* and *Discussant* (b). The *Discussant* is prompted to listen to the opinion of the *Opponent* around the discussion statement and may then accept, reject, or ignore such opinion (c) and update their current one accordingly by ± 1 (d).

77 in persuasive interactions: when agents holding opposing views interact, movement toward endorsing the
78 discussion statement is more likely than movement toward rejecting it, even in balanced populations. At
79 the collective level, its effect depends on exposure: heterogeneous networks allow this bias to propagate and
80 produce rapid convergence, whereas homophily and large disagreeing majorities limit cross-opinion encoun-
81 ters and lead to persistent polarization. Providing agents with information about their local neighborhood
82 further reshapes the dynamics by favouring moderate agreement and making opinion change contingent on
83 local alignment.

84
85 The remainder of this work is organized as follows. In Section 2, we provide an overview of the litera-
86 ture regarding opinion dynamics and LLM agents. In Section 3, we introduce the framework for LLM opinion
87 dynamics, and in Section 4, we introduce the experimental setup and results. Finally, in Section 5, we
88 conclude the work by discussing the results and suggesting future research directions.

89 2 Related Work

90 In this section, we discuss relevant literature on Opinion Dynamics and Large Language Model-augmented
91 social simulations.

92 **Opinion Dynamic Models** Opinion dynamics (OD) describes computational processes that mimic how
93 individual views evolve over time under empirically observed social influences [39, 40]. In a typical OD simu-
94 lation, a network of interacting agents—the *population*—holds opinions encoded as real numbers. Empirically
95 grounded social mechanisms are cast as update rules, drawing on techniques from statistical physics, such as
96 graph theory, probability, and statistical modeling. For example, an agent may revise its stance by randomly
97 copying a neighbor’s opinion [41] (modeling imitation), by averaging the views in its local neighborhood [42]
98 (capturing homophily [30]), or by adopting the most frequent opinion around it [43] (reflecting peer pressure
99 and mutual awareness [44]). OD research asks whether the interplay of these mechanisms drives the system
100 toward one of three mutually exclusive collective states: (i) *consensus*, when all agents share the same view;
101 (ii) *polarization*, when opinions cluster around two opposing poles; or (iii) *fragmentation*, when more than
102 two distinct clusters form [45, 46].

103 OD models are also classified by how they encode the opinion variable. In *discrete* models, opinions can
104 take only a finite set of values, with rules specifying switches among them. The classic Voter Model [47], for
105 instance, considers populations in which agents adopt one of two opposing stances (e.g., agree/disagree). By
106 contrast, *continuous* models treat opinions as points on an uninterrupted spectrum. Canonical examples,

107 such as the DeGroot Model [48], allow any value within a bounded interval – commonly $[-1, 1]$ – and
 108 interactions move opinions smoothly along that continuum.

109 **Large Language Models** Recent studies have examined the dynamics that arise from interactions among
 110 large language models (LLMs). These LLM agents typically exhibit realistic behavior both individually and
 111 collectively [13, 14], with human-like patterns naturally emerging from their interactions. Examples include
 112 the formation of scale-free networks [49], dissemination of information [50], and the development of trust [51].
 113 When supplied with demographic backgrounds and personality traits, LLMs can more accurately mimic hu-
 114 man behavior [13, 52, 53], including reflecting human biases and political inclinations [54]. Integrating LLMs
 115 with traditional agent-based modeling approaches [55], as demonstrated in [56], has shown how recommender
 116 systems can influence the quality of discourse. Specifically, agents exposed to popular content tend to exhibit
 117 increased toxicity and interparty engagement, mirroring the toxicity levels seen in U.S. Twitter discourse
 118 circa 2019. Further simulations reveal that confirmation bias among agents contributes to social fragmen-
 119 tation [57], aligning with established findings in opinion dynamics. LLMs are also capable of emulating
 120 persuasive communication [29, 58], generating coherent arguments based on psycho-linguistic theories of
 121 opinion change, and can be utilized for comprehensive social media simulations [18]. Nonetheless, LLMs
 122 have a natural inclination toward factual correctness and often resist generating content that contradicts
 123 scientific knowledge unless explicitly prompted [57]. This tendency may cause them to disregard assigned
 124 roles or personality traits [15], resulting in less authentic behavior. Additionally, LLM agents generally avoid
 125 intense conflict [56, 59] and display sensitivity toward various social and political issues [60, 61].

126 3 LLM-powered Opinion Dynamics

127 We present a general framework to describe how populations of large language model (LLM) agents develop
 128 and revise opinions through structured interactions [62]. The system is represented by the tuple:

$$\mathfrak{F} = \langle \mathcal{G}, \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{O}, f, T, \mathcal{D} \rangle,$$

129 where each element captures a specific component of the simulation:

- 130 • $\mathcal{G} = \langle V, E \rangle$ denotes the interaction network, where V is the set of LLM agents and $E \subseteq V \times V$ is the set
 131 of undirected pairs of agents that can interact. The topology may be fully connected (i.e., mean-field)
 132 or follow an empirical or synthetic configuration.
- 133 • \mathcal{S} is the discussion prompt or proposition that defines the initial subject of deliberation. It establishes
 134 the semantic dimension along which opinions are assessed.
- 135 • \mathcal{O} represents the space of admissible opinions. This space can be discrete (e.g., $\mathcal{O} = \{0, 1\}$) or con-
 136 tinuous (e.g., $\mathcal{O} = [0, 1]$), encoding positions from complete disagreement to full agreement with the
 137 statement \mathcal{S} .
- 138 • $f : \mathcal{O}^n \times \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathcal{O}$ is the opinion update function. It specifies how an agent revises its opinion as
 139 a function of its current position, the opinions of n neighboring agents, and additional features or
 140 external variables in \mathbb{R}^m .
- 141 • T is the temporal domain of the simulation, defined as an ordered sequence of discrete time steps
 142 $t \in \mathbb{Z}^+$.
- 143 • $\mathcal{D}(t) = \{o_i(t) \mid i \in V\}$ denotes the opinion state at time t , where $o_i(t) \in \mathcal{O}$ is the opinion of agent i at
 144 that time.

145 This framework supports a wide variety of network topologies, interaction mechanisms, and opinion evo-
 146 lution rules. In what follows, we describe a particular instantiation of the model adopted in our experimental
 147 setting.

148 A general overview of its rationale is provided in Figure 2. In detail, we define the graph topology,
 149 the initial statement, the opinion distribution, and the number of iterations. Each agent is initialized with

Figure 2: LLM Opinion Dynamics

Require: Graph: \mathcal{G} , Statement: \mathcal{S} , Initial opinions: $\mathcal{D}(0) = \{o_i(0) \mid i \in V\}$, Time steps: T_{\max} ,
Ensure: Opinion Distribution Evolution \mathcal{D}_{all}

```

1: Init  $\mathcal{D}_{all}$  as an empty list
2:  $\mathcal{D}_{all}.\text{append}(\mathcal{D}(0))$ 
3: for  $t = 0$  to  $T_{\max} - 1$  do
4:   for each agent  $i \in V$  do
5:     Select random neighbor  $v_j \in \text{Neighbors}(i)$ 
6:      $\Delta o_i(t) = \text{debate}(o_i(t), o_j(t), \mathcal{S})$ 
7:     Update opinion:  $o_i(t+1) = o_i(t) + \Delta o_i(t)$ 
8:   end for
9:   Update opinion distribution:  $\mathcal{D}(t+1) = \{o_i(t+1) \mid i \in V\}$ 
10:   $\mathcal{D}_{all}.\text{append}(\mathcal{D}(t+1))$ 
11: end for
12: return  $\mathcal{D}_{all}$ 

```

Figure 3: Debate

Require: Initial opinions: o_i, o_j , Statement: \mathcal{S} , Maximum number of interaction rounds: max_rounds
Ensure: Final opinion delta of the Discussant: $o_i^{\Delta+}$

```

1: Init Discussant's Opinion Delta  $o_i^{\Delta+} \leftarrow 0$ 
2: Discussant states its opinion  $o_i$  on  $\mathcal{S}$ 
3: for  $\text{round} = 1$  to  $\text{max\_rounds} = 3$  do
4:   Opponent's Turn:
5:   Opponent evaluates Discussant's argument
6:   Opponent decides and justifies: ACCEPT, REJECT, IGNORE
7:   if decision is IGNORE or ACCEPT then
8:     break
9:   end if
10:  Discussant's Turn:
11:  Discussant evaluates Opponent's argument
12:  Discussant decides and justifies: ACCEPT, REJECT, IGNORE
13:  if decision is ACCEPT then
14:     $o_i^{\Delta+} \leftarrow 1$  if  $o_j > o_i$  else  $-1$ 
15:    break
16:  else if decision is REJECT then
17:     $o_i^{\Delta+} \leftarrow -1$  if  $o_j > o_i$  else  $1$ 
18:    break
19:  end if
20: end for
21: return  $o_i^{\Delta+}$ 

```

150 a discrete opinion on a 7-point Likert scale, such that 0 corresponds with strong disagreement with \mathcal{S} , 3
151 corresponds with neutrality, and 6 denotes strong agreement. At each time step, for each agent $i \in V$, a
152 neighbor j is randomly selected to engage in a debate on \mathcal{S} . As a result of the debate, i 's opinion is either
153 (i) brought closer to j 's if they agree, (ii) brought farther from j 's if they disagree, or (iii) not modified if
154 j 's arguments are ignored. Opinion updates are stored at each iteration and returned at the end.

155
156 The debate unfolds according to Figure 3. The selected agents are first assigned one of two mutually
157 exclusive roles, namely discussant (agent i) or opponent (agent j). The discussant is the agent who starts
158 the conversation. It does so by expressing and justifying its opinion on \mathcal{S} . The discussant is the only agent
159 allowed to change its opinion (after engaging with the opponent). The opponent is tasked with producing
160 a persuasive argument to convince the discussant. It is a stubborn agent, i.e., it is not allowed to change
161 opinion. The debate proceeds in rounds, where each round consists of one interaction from each agent. The
162 total number of rounds is capped by a maximum limit, max_rounds , to ensure the debate does not continue
163 indefinitely. Initially, the Discussant is prompted to express its opinion on \mathcal{S} .¹ During each round, the
164 Opponent first evaluates the Discussant's message and then decides whether to ACCEPT, REJECT, or IGNORE
165 the Discussant's viewpoint. If the Opponent chooses to IGNORE or ACCEPT, the debate concludes. Otherwise,
166 the Discussant evaluates the Opponent's argument, and the debate continues. The final opinion shift of the
167 Discussant, $o_i^{\Delta+}$, is determined based on its final choice. If the Discussant ACCEPTS, its opinion is brought
168 closer to the Opponent's, and if it REJECTS, it is brought further (e.g., backfire effect [63]). If the Discussant
169 does neither, or if the debate terminates earlier, their opinion remains unchanged.

¹Generated data and code are available at: [10.5281/zenodo.19594766](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19594766)

4 Results

We conduct a series of simulations within the LLM-based opinion dynamics framework introduced in Section 3. We generate scale-free networks of 100 agents in which nodes belong to two mutually exclusive classes, with tunable class sizes and assortativity [36]. For further information on the network generation process, please refer to Appendix A. The discussion prompt is based on the paradox of Theseus’ Ship, first reported in Plutarch’s *Parallel Lives* [64], which questions whether an object that has had all its components replaced retains its identity. The statement is deliberately non-empirical to avoid convergence driven by factual correctness and to preserve argumentative diversity [38, 57]. Unless otherwise stated, results are obtained with Llama 3.1 [3], and the neighborhood-pressure condition is additionally replicated with Gemma3 [65]. For each parameter configuration we run a single simulation on a fixed network realization in order to isolate the structural effect of the experimental parameters and to avoid compounding sources of stochasticity.

Experimental design. We begin with a symmetric configuration in which the two opinion groups are equally represented, providing a baseline to evaluate how homophily ($h \in [0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1]$) affects opinion diffusion in the absence of numerical advantage (RQ1). We then introduce asymmetric populations in which one group constitutes 30% and 10% of the agents to assess the impact of minority size on global dynamics (RQ2). Each imbalance condition is repeated in a reverse configuration, where the initial majority and minority positions are swapped, to test whether the outcomes depend on the opinion side rather than on group size alone (RQ3). Finally, we provide agents with information about the opinion distribution in their ego network during the interaction to evaluate the effect of local social pressure on opinion change (RQ4).

We first examine the temporal evolution and final distribution of opinions across all scenarios, thereby identifying the macro-level effects of homophily and group composition. We then focus on the neighborhood-pressure condition and estimate opinion transition probability matrices to uncover the micro-level mechanisms driving the observed patterns. These probabilities quantify the likelihood that a Discussant moves toward the Opponent’s position under different initial configurations and neighborhood states. To assess whether the observed transition probabilities differ from what would be expected by chance, we employ a permutation-based null model. Specifically, we randomly reshuffle the post-interaction opinions among interaction events while keeping fixed (i) the pre-interaction opinions of both agents and (ii) the neighborhood composition. This procedure preserves the marginal distributions and the interaction structure but removes any systematic association between interaction context and opinion change. For each entry of the transition matrix, we generate a null distribution from 1000 permutations and retain only those probabilities that are significantly different from the null expectation ($p < 0.01$). Details on the estimation and validation procedure are reported in Appendix B.

4.1 Effect of homophily and group size imbalance

Opinion trajectories for all configurations are shown in Figures 4 and 5. We first discuss the symmetric population (RQ1), then introduce class imbalance (RQ2), and finally analyze the reverse configurations (RQ3).

Balanced Scenario (RQ1). With equal group sizes, all networks with $0 \leq h \leq 0.75$ rapidly converge toward the positive side of the opinion scale, typically within 20–40 iterations (Figure 4a). Lower homophily accelerates convergence, with heterophilic networks reaching agreement almost immediately. As h increases, convergence becomes slower, but the final outcome remains unchanged. A qualitatively different regime emerges at complete homophily ($h = 1$), where interactions occur almost exclusively within like-minded groups, and the system stabilizes in a segregated, polarized state.

Imbalanced Scenario (RQ2). Introducing a minority strengthens the convergence toward agreement. With a 70/30 split, the system reaches consensus in about 20–30 iterations across all homophily levels, with only minor fluctuations between *agree* and *strongly agree* (Figure 4b). Similarly to the balanced scenario, high homophily ($h = 0.75$) slows convergence speed; nonetheless, the agents reach perfect adherence to the strongly agree opinion. Reducing the minority to 10% further accelerates its disappearance, especially for $0 \leq h \leq 0.25$, while higher homophily temporarily preserves small opposing clusters before convergence

Figure 4: **Opinion trends for the base scenario (strongly-agreeing majority) across different homophily levels for minority fraction $min=0.5$ (a), $min = 0.3$ (b) and $min = 0.1$ (c)** Each panel shows the proportion of agents holding different opinion states over 100 iterations. All points of the opinion scale are mapped to the colors in the legend, from *Strongly Disagree* (dark red) to *Strongly Agree* (dark green).

Figure 5: **Opinion trends for the reversed scenario (strongly-disagreeing majority) across different homophily levels for minority fraction $\min=0.5$ (a), $\min = 0.3$ (b), and $\min = 0.1$ (c)** Each panel shows the proportion of agents holding different opinion states over 100 iterations with different levels of homophily. All points of the opinion scale are mapped to the colors in the legend, from *Strongly Disagree* (dark red) to *Strongly Agree* (dark green).

221 (Figure 4c). At $h = 1$, segregation persists because cross-group interactions are rare.

222

223 **Reversed Imbalanced Scenario (RQ3).** Interestingly, when moving to the reverse class distribution
 224 scenario, where the minority now holds the *strongly agree* opinion, trends show a clear pattern that di-
 225 verges from simple symmetry (Figure 5). With $\min = 0.3$, disagreeing agents form a dominant cluster, with
 226 small neutral and agreeing clusters surviving for several iterations. Although the latter gradually decreases
 227 in size after 40 iterations, the dominant opinion does not reach full consensus. This pattern persists for
 228 $0.25 \leq h \leq 0.75$, indicating that negative majorities are more resistant to complete convergence. Strength-
 229 ening the imbalance at $\min = 0.1$ heightens the dominance of strongly disagreeing opinion clusters across
 230 all homophily levels, with only small residual agreeing clusters. Only in the case of $h = 1$, agents behave
 231 almost symmetrically to what was previously observed in the base imbalanced scenario, which we attribute
 232 to strong structural constraints.

233 4.2 Effect of neighborhood awareness

234 Providing agents with the distribution of opinions in their ego network results in systematically faster opinion
 235 change and shifts the dynamics toward moderate agreement (Figure 6a). In the balanced population, conver-
 236 gence is almost immediate but typically stops at *agree*, also preventing the full convergence observed without
 237 neighborhood information. Under complete homophily ($h = 1$), agents initially maintain separation between
 238 the two extreme clusters; then, an additional cluster with the *agree* opinion emerges. With moderate class
 239 imbalance, neighborhood awareness eliminates the rapid dominance of extreme positive opinions observed
 240 in the base scenario and allows small neutral and mildly positive clusters to persist across homophily levels
 241 (Figure 6b). Under extreme class imbalance, the majority of opinions stabilize on *agree*, followed by a few
 242 *strongly agree* and minimal other clusters (Figure 6c). Interestingly, the polarized outcome between extreme
 243 stances observed so far at $h = 1$ does not hold in this scenario; here, we note an *agree* majority followed by
 244 small *mildly agree* and *neutral* clusters. In other words, unlike other high-homophily settings, the minority
 245 slowly moves toward the majority’s opinion under extreme class imbalance and known neighborhood con-
 246 figuration. In the reverse configurations, where the minority initially holds the positive stance (Figures 7a

247 and 7b), the dynamics become asymmetric. For $min = 0.3$, negatively oriented majorities progressively shift
 248 toward moderate and positive positions, indicating that access to neighborhood opinion distributions miti-
 249 gates the dominance of negative opinions; a stable negative cluster persists only under complete homophily
 250 ($h = 1$), where interactions remain within groups. In the extreme imbalance ($min = 0.1$), however, the
 251 negative majority instead consolidates and converges, a process reinforced by homophily, while the small
 252 positive minority survives only in fully homophilic networks without changing its stance.

Figure 6: **Opinion trends for the base scenario (strongly-agreeing majority) under neighborhood opinion awareness across different homophily levels for minority fraction $min=0.5$ (a), $min = 0.3$ (b), and $min = 0.1$ (c)** Each panel shows the proportion of agents holding different opinion states over 100 iterations. All points of the opinion scale are mapped to the colors in the legend, from *Strongly Disagree* (dark red) to *Strongly Agree* (dark green).

253 4.2.1 Model Comparison

254 The Gemma-based simulations reveal a systematically stronger drift toward positive opinions than observed
 255 with Llama. In balanced populations, negatively oriented agents disappear rapidly for all $0 \leq h \leq 0.75$, and
 256 the system converges either to *strongly agree* or to a polarized configuration dominated by a large positive
 257 cluster (Figure 8). Even under complete homophily, where Llama agents remain segregated at the two ex-
 258 tremes, Gemma agents predominantly reinforce the positive side, indicating a higher intrinsic propensity to
 259 accept upward shifts. This tendency is further amplified in imbalanced settings: when the positive class is
 260 the majority, intermediate opinions vanish quickly, and convergence toward the positive extreme is faster
 261 and more stable than in the corresponding Llama runs.

262
 263 The asymmetry persists in the reverse configurations, where negative agents form the numerical major-

Figure 7: **Opinion trends for the reversed scenario (strongly-disagreeing majority) under neighborhood awareness across different homophily levels for minority fraction $min=0.5$ (a), $min = 0.3$ (b), and $min = 0.1$ (c)** Each panel shows the proportion of agents holding different opinion states over 100 iterations. All points of the opinion scale are mapped to the colors in the legend, from *Strongly Disagree* (dark red) to *Strongly Agree* (dark green).

264 ity. Although negative clusters initially survive for several iterations, upward transitions remain frequent
 265 and the dynamics eventually lead to either strong polarization or to the re-emergence of a dominant positive
 266 cluster. This behavior suggests that Gemma agents are less sensitive to structural constraints and
 267 more responsive to persuasive interactions that point toward agreement. At the micro level, this is reflected
 268 in transition probabilities close to 1 for low-to-high shifts and in the high stability of high-opinion states,
 269 confirming a stronger and more persistent bias toward positive opinions compared with Llama.

270 4.2.2 Neighborhood Awareness and Interaction Dynamics

271 To connect the aggregate opinion trajectories with the underlying interaction dynamics, we analyze condi-
 272 tional transition probability matrices for balanced populations ($min = 0.5$). Across all homophily levels and
 273 model variants, upward transitions (low \rightarrow high) are consistently more likely than downward ones (high \rightarrow
 274 low), indicating that persuasion is structurally asymmetric and biased toward positive opinions (Figure 9).
 275 This asymmetry, which we will refer to as *agreement drift*, persists even when group sizes are equal, showing
 276 that it is not a consequence of numerical dominance, but likely an intrinsic feature of the LLM interaction
 277 dynamics. Increasing homophily reduces the frequency of cross-opinion encounters and leads to structural
 278 segregation, yet the imbalance between upward and downward shifts remains visible whenever interactions
 279 between opposite opinions occur.

280 Providing agents with knowledge of their neighbors' opinion distributions (Figure 9, mid row) produces
 281 distinctive behavior: agents seem to change their opinion when facing a higher-opinion opponent, but be-
 282 come more resistant to changing their opinion when facing a lower-opinion opponent. The most interesting
 283 scenario is $h = 1$, as discussants holding a low opinion prefer high-opinion opponents (83%), while the
 284 reverse transition occurs (100%), indicating that persuasion remains active despite structural segregation.
 285 Maintaining a high opinion, however, seems difficult for high-opinion agents, as their likelihood of retaining
 286 it is relatively low (30%), especially compared with the base scenario. The effect is even stronger for Gemma
 287 agents (Figure 9, bottom row), for which upward transitions approach probability 1 and high-opinion states
 288 become highly stable.

289 To further assess the impact of agents' knowledge of their neighbors' opinion distribution, we quantify

(a) $min=0.5$

(b) $min=0.3$

(c) $min=0.1$

(d) Reverse with $min=0.3$

(e) Reverse with $min=0.1$

Figure 8: **Opinion trends under neighborhood awareness across homophily levels.** Panels (a–c) show the base scenario (strongly agreeing majority) for minority fractions $m = 0.5$, $m = 0.3$, and $m = 0.1$, respectively; panels (d–e) show the reversed scenario (strongly disagreeing majority) for $m = 0.3$ and $m = 0.1$. Each panel reports the proportion of agents in each opinion state over 100 iterations. colors map the 7-point scale from *Strongly Disagree* (dark red) to *Strongly Agree* (dark green).

Figure 9: Conditional probabilities of persuasion in pairwise interactions between LLM agents. Each matrix reports $P(\text{disc} \rightarrow \text{opp} \mid o_{\text{disc}}, o_{\text{opp}})$ for balanced populations ($\min = 0.5$), with the 7-point scale collapsed into low- and high-opinion macrostates. Rows correspond to the discussant’s initial opinion and columns to the opponent’s. Panels compare homophily levels (h) and interaction settings (base vs. neighborhood-aware). Only statistically significant probabilities are shown.

290 the likelihood of the deviation of the discussants’ final opinions in relation to their neighbors in the opinion-
 291 distribution-aware setting. These matrices were created for both Llama (Figure 10) and Gemma simulations
 292 (Figure 11).

293 For Llama agents, opposing neighborhoods strongly stabilize high-opinion discussants, whose probability
 294 of maintaining their position remains close to one across all h . At the same time, upward shifts from low
 295 to high emerge even when the local environment discourages them, becoming deterministic for $h = 0.75$.
 296 Mixed neighborhoods display the most symmetric dynamics, with statistically significant transitions in both
 297 directions for $h \leq 0.75$. For $h \leq 0.75$, transitions from high to low become more significant, allowing a down-
 298 ward movement from high to low. In supporting neighborhoods, opinion change largely follows the local
 299 consensus: shifts aligned with the neighborhood are reinforced, while the persistence of low-opinion states in
 300 low-to-low interactions remains rare. Overall, peer pressure acts as a selective amplifier [66], strengthening
 301 changes that are locally consistent, while still allowing occasional counter-aligned upward moves.

302
 303 Gemma exhibits a qualitatively different regime. Most cross-class shift probabilities are not significant,
 304 especially when the direction of the shift is supported or opposed by neighboring agents. The most no-
 305 ticeable patterns appear in the first (opposing) and third (supporting) rows of the matrices in Figure 11.
 306 In opposing neighborhoods, statistically significant shifts in probability occur from low to high opinions,
 307 indicating that Gemma agents can adjust upward even when surrounded by opposing agents. Conversely,
 308 with supporting agents and in all homophily configurations, discussants move from high to low. Agents in
 309 this case are susceptible to neighborhood alignment and change their opinion when their peers reinforce this
 310 transition. Additionally, with high homophily values ($0.75 \leq h \leq 1$), only shifts probabilities consistent
 311 with each agent’s ego network are allowed. According to this dynamic, opinion change is allowed only when
 312 contextual reinforcement is sufficiently strong. Therefore, Gemma exhibits a different behavior to Llama,
 313 with rare opinion shifts in which agents are subjected to peer pressure from the neighborhood during class
 314 changes. The bias toward acceptance is more evident in Gemma, where low-to-high transitions are allowed

Figure 10: Facet plots of statistically significant opinion shifts for Llama agents under different neighborhood conditions. Each panel reports $P(\text{disc} \rightarrow \text{opp} \mid o_{\text{disc}}, o_{\text{opp}}, c)$, where $c \in \{\text{aligned}, \text{misaligned}, \text{mixed}\}$ denotes the discussant’s local neighborhood configuration. Rows correspond to aligned, misaligned, and mixed neighborhoods, while columns vary the homophily level h . Only statistically significant transitions are shown.

315 even in the presence of an opposing neighborhood. In the mixed scenario, Gemma’s agents exhibit more
 316 varied behavior, as they are not exposed to a single dominant opinion. The matrices show interaction prob-
 317 abilities that are statistically significant across all homophily levels, with a preference for agents to accept
 318 high-to-high opinion shifts.

319 5 Discussion

320 This work investigates how network structure, class imbalance, and local social information shape opinion
 321 dynamics in populations of LLM agents, and to what extent the resulting collective behavior resembles
 322 mechanisms known from human social systems. This study identifies two main results that jointly explain
 323 the collective behavior of LLM-based opinion dynamics.

324
 325 First, we observe a systematic bias we term **agreement drift**: in pairwise interactions, agents are more
 326 likely to shift from lower to higher positions on the opinion scale than in the opposite direction. Across
 327 homophily levels, class distributions, and model variants, upward transitions occur more frequently than
 328 downward ones whenever agents holding opposing views interact. A similar effect was reported in pre-
 329 vious work [38, 67]; here we show that it generalizes across different models and heterogeneous network
 330 configurations. We find that this asymmetry is present even in balanced populations, indicating that it is
 331 not dependent on numerical dominance and cannot be reduced to a majority effect. At the same time, it
 332 does not automatically produce convergence toward agreement at the collective level: when cross-opinion
 333 encounters are limited (either because the disagreeing group forms a large majority or because homophily
 334 segregates the network) the directional tendency remains locally observable but cannot spread through the
 335 system. Collective outcomes, therefore, emerge from the interaction between an intrinsic persuasive bias and
 336 the opportunity structure for exposure created by the network.

Figure 11: Facet plots of statistically significant opinion shifts for Llama agents under different neighborhood conditions. Each panel reports $P(\text{disc} \rightarrow \text{opp} \mid o_{\text{disc}}, o_{\text{opp}}, c)$, where $c \in \{\text{aligned, misaligned, mixed}\}$ denotes the discussant’s local neighborhood configuration. Rows correspond to aligned, misaligned, and mixed neighborhoods, while columns vary the homophily level h . Only statistically significant transitions are shown.

337

338 Importantly, the agreement drift effect is distinct from the sycophantic behavior documented in prior
339 work [15, 68–70]. Sycophancy is the tendency of an LLM to align with a user’s explicitly stated belief
340 (regardless of truth or epistemic consistency) in order to maximise perceived helpfulness/social approval.
341 Agreement drift, by contrast, is a directional susceptibility in which positions expressing endorsement of
342 the discussion statement exert systematically greater persuasive pull than positions expressing rejection. In
343 other words, when agents holding opposing views interact, movement toward the pro-position is more likely
344 than toward the contra-position, regardless of who initially holds the majority, and without any external
345 reward for compliance.

346

347 The second main result concerns the role of **structural and contextual constraints** in modulating this
348 intrinsic tendency. Homophily regulates the reach of the directional bias by controlling the frequency of
349 cross-opinion encounters. At low and moderate levels of homophily, heterogeneous exposure enables the
350 asymmetric persuasive mechanism to propagate through the population, leading to rapid convergence to-
351 ward agreement even in the absence of a numerical advantage. At high homophily, by contrast, the same
352 bias becomes trapped within segregated clusters, leading the system to stabilize in polarized configurations.
353 Class imbalance acts as an additional gatekeeper: large disagreeing majorities can prevent the diffusion of
354 agreement drift by reducing the probability of encounters with pro-position agents, while small minorities
355 disappear quickly when exposure is high. Providing agents with information about their local neighbor-
356 hood introduces a further layer of mediation. Rather than simply accelerating convergence, neighborhood
357 awareness reshapes the outcome by favouring moderate agreement and by making opinion change contingent
358 on local alignment, thereby revealing a mechanism analogous to peer-pressure effects in classical opinion-
359 dynamics models.

360

361 **Implications.** Our findings have direct methodological implications for the use of LLM agents as proxy-
362 es for human behavior in computational social science. In many empirical and theoretical models of human
363 opinion dynamics, persuasive influence is assumed to be directionally neutral and collective outcomes are pri-
364 marily attributed to network topology, initial conditions, and exposure patterns [46, 66, 71, 72]. In the LLM
365 populations studied here, by contrast, the micro-level persuasive interaction is intrinsically asymmetric due
366 to agreement drift. This shows that *convergence in LLM-based social simulations cannot be interpreted as*
367 *evidence of consensus dynamics without first characterising the model’s intrinsic persuasion tendency.* This
368 means that simulations employing LLM agents may systematically overestimate the emergence of consensus
369 whenever cross-opinion encounters are sufficiently frequent, and conversely, attribute persistent disagreement
370 to segregation even when a directional persuasive tendency is present at the interaction level. For the grow-
371 ing literature that treats LLM populations as behavioral surrogates for human groups, this result highlights
372 the need to disentangle structural effects from model-intrinsic interaction biases before drawing substantive
373 conclusions about social processes.

374

375 **Limitations and Future Directions.** Several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the results
376 are obtained for a specific interaction protocol and a single non-factual discussion topic; although the agree-
377 ment drift is likely not a consequence of our interaction procedure because it emerges even under different
378 configurations [38, 67], different prompting strategies or semantically grounded statements may alter its
379 strength. Second, we consider networks of fixed size and a specific generative model; larger populations
380 and/or alternative topologies may introduce additional mesoscopic effects. Third, the strong differences
381 observed between LLM families call for a systematic analysis across models. Addressing these aspects is
382 essential to determine which behavioral patterns are model-specific and which represent general properties
383 of LLM societies. Future work should therefore investigate how heterogeneous agent profiles, memory, and
384 repeated interactions affect the persistence of minority opinions, and calibrate LLM-based dynamics against
385 empirical human data to assess their behavioral realism. Understanding how intrinsic agreement biases in-
386 teract with algorithmic mediation and recommender systems is also crucial for evaluating the risk of artificial
387 consensus formation in human–AI hybrid environments.

388 A Networks with Controlled Homophily and Group Size

389 To address our research questions, we need to generate networks with controlled group sizes (i.e., node
 390 attribute frequencies) and mixing biases (i.e., nodes’ preferences for connecting with similar/dissimilar peers).
 391 To do so, we leverage the *BA-homophily* model introduced in [36], which extends the classical Barabási–Albert
 392 (BA) preferential attachment model [36] by incorporating a *homophily* parameter. The classic BA model [73]
 393 is a foundational generative model for scale-free networks. It captures two key mechanisms underlying many
 394 real-world complex systems: *network growth* and *preferential attachment*. The model starts with a small
 395 connected network of m_0 nodes. At each time step, a new node is added to the network and forms $m \leq m_0$
 396 links to existing nodes. The probability Π_i that the new node connects to an existing node i is proportional
 397 to the degree k_i of that node:

$$\Pi_i = \frac{k_i}{\sum_j k_j}$$

398 This rule encodes *preferential attachment*, where well-connected nodes are more likely to attract additional
 399 links, a “rich-get-richer” dynamic. Over time, this process generates networks with a power-law degree dis-
 400 tribution, $P(k) \propto k^{-\gamma}$, with $\gamma \approx 3$.

401
 402 The BA-homophily enriches this framework in two ways. First, each node belongs to one of two groups,
 403 a (minority) or b (majority), with group sizes defined by relative proportions f_a and $f_b = 1 - f_a$, where
 404 $f_a \leq f_b$. Second, when a new node j arrives, it selects m existing nodes to connect to, choosing targets
 405 based on both their degree and group similarity. Formally, the probability Π_{ij} that node j connects to node
 406 i is given by:

$$\Pi_{ij} = \frac{h_{ij} \cdot k_i}{\sum_l h_{lj} \cdot k_l},$$

407 where k_i is the degree of node i and h_{ij} encodes homophilic preference. In the symmetric case where
 408 node groups show equal homophilic preferences, we have that

$$h_{aa} = h_{bb} = h, \quad h_{ab} = h_{ba} = 1 - h$$

409 Via this mechanism, the model can generate networks with complete heterophily (nodes only connect to
 410 the opposite group, $h = 0$), neutral mixing (no group preference, classical BA, $h = 0.5$), up to complete
 411 homophily (nodes only connect within their group, $h = 1$). As shown in [36], in heterophilic networks
 412 ($h < 0.5$), minority nodes become structural hubs, attracting a disproportionate number of links from the
 413 majority. Conversely, in homophilic settings ($h > 0.5$), they become increasingly segregated.

414 B Opinion Transition Probabilities and Validation

415 To uncover the mechanisms underlying the observed opinion dynamics, we analyze micro-level interaction
 416 patterns between *Discussant* and *Opponent* agents. Specifically, we construct transition probability matrices
 417 that quantify the likelihood that a Discussant shifts its opinion toward that of the Opponent following an
 418 interaction, conditional on the Discussant’s and Opponent’s initial opinion class. Formally, we estimate:

$$P(\text{disc} \rightarrow \text{opp} \mid o_{\text{disc}}, o_{\text{opp}}),$$

419 where $\text{disc} \rightarrow \text{opp}$ denotes a change in the Discussant’s opinion toward the Opponent’s position, o_{disc} is the
 420 Discussant’s initial opinion, and o_{opp} is the Opponent’s opinion. By doing so, we aim to estimate the rate of
 421 successful (as in persuasive) interactions.

422
 423 For the simulations in which agents are equipped with information on their neighbors’ opinion distribution,
 424 we additionally condition this probability on the Discussant’s local neighborhood configuration, distinguish-
 425 ing whether its neighbors are aligned, misaligned, or mixed, with respect to the direction of change. This
 426 extension isolates the effect of peer agreement on opinion shifts. Formally:

$$P(\text{disc} \rightarrow \text{opp} \mid o_{\text{disc}}, o_{\text{opp}}, c),$$

427 where $c \in \{\text{aligned, misaligned, mixed}\}$ denotes the configuration of the Discussant’s neighborhood relative
428 to the direction of the potential opinion shift, that is, whether the majority of the Discussant’s neighbors
429 hold opinions that are closer to the Opponent’s position (aligned), closer to the Discussant’s initial position
430 (misaligned), or are evenly split between the two (mixed).

431

432 To identify statistically significant transitions, we adopt a permutation-based null model that tests whether
433 the observed association between opinion pairs and the direction of change exceeds what would be expected
434 by chance. For each interaction, we keep the pair (o_{disc}, o_{opp}) (resp. (o_{disc}, o_{opp}, c) for the extension) fixed
435 and randomly shuffle the observed opinion variations across interactions. This procedure preserves the em-
436 pirical distribution of opinion changes as well as the frequency of each opinion pair, while removing any
437 systematic relationship between them. For every permutation, we recompute the transition probabilities,
438 thereby obtaining a null distribution for each conditioning configuration. The statistical significance of the
439 observed probability is then assessed using a two-tailed test, defined as the fraction of null values that are
440 at least as extreme as the empirical estimate.

441 References

- 442 [1] OpenAI, Josh Achiam, Steven Adler, Sandhini Agarwal, Lama Ahmad, Ilge Akkaya, Florencia Leoni Ale-
443 man, Diogo Almeida, Janko Altenschmidt, Sam Altman, Shyamal Anadkat, Red Avila, Igor Babuschkin,
444 Suchir Balaji, Valerie Balcom, Paul Baltescu, Haiming Bao, Mohammad Bavarian, Jeff Belgum, Irwan
445 Bello, Jake Berdine, Gabriel Bernadett-Shapiro, Christopher Berner, Lenny Bogdonoff, Oleg Boiko,
446 Madelaine Boyd, Anna-Luisa Brakman, Greg Brockman, Tim Brooks, Miles Brundage, Kevin Button,
447 Trevor Cai, Rosie Campbell, Andrew Cann, Brittany Carey, Chelsea Carlson, Rory Carmichael, Brooke
448 Chan, Che Chang, Fotis Chantzis, Derek Chen, Sully Chen, Ruby Chen, Jason Chen, Mark Chen,
449 Ben Chess, Chester Cho, Casey Chu, Hyung Won Chung, Dave Cummings, Jeremiah Currier, Yunxing
450 Dai, Cory Decareaux, Thomas Degry, Noah Deutsch, Damien Deville, Arka Dhar, David Dohan, Steve
451 Dowling, Sheila Dunning, Adrien Ecoffet, Atty Eleti, Tyna Eloundou, David Farhi, Liam Fedus, Niko
452 Felix, Simón Posada Fishman, Juston Forte, Isabella Fulford, Leo Gao, Elie Georges, Christian Gibson,
453 Vik Goel, Tarun Gogineni, Gabriel Goh, Rapha Gontijo-Lopes, Jonathan Gordon, Morgan Grafstein,
454 Scott Gray, Ryan Greene, Joshua Gross, Shixiang Shane Gu, Yufei Guo, Chris Hallacy, Jesse Han,
455 Jeff Harris, Yuchen He, Mike Heaton, Johannes Heidecke, Chris Hesse, Alan Hickey, Wade Hickey, Pe-
456 ter Hoeschele, Brandon Houghton, Kenny Hsu, Shengli Hu, Xin Hu, Joost Huizinga, Shantanu Jain,
457 Shawn Jain, Joanne Jang, Angela Jiang, Roger Jiang, Haozhun Jin, Denny Jin, Shino Jomoto, Billie
458 Jonn, Heewoo Jun, Tomer Kaftan, Łukasz Kaiser, Ali Kamali, Ingmar Kanitscheider, Nitish Shirish
459 Keskar, Tabarak Khan, Logan Kilpatrick, Jong Wook Kim, Christina Kim, Yongjik Kim, Jan Hendrik
460 Kirchner, Jamie Kiros, Matt Knight, Daniel Kokotajlo, Łukasz Kondraciuk, Andrew Kondrich, Aris
461 Konstantinidis, Kyle Kosic, Gretchen Krueger, Vishal Kuo, Michael Lampe, Ikai Lan, Teddy Lee, Jan
462 Leike, Jade Leung, Daniel Levy, Chak Ming Li, Rachel Lim, Molly Lin, Stephanie Lin, Mateusz Litwin,
463 Theresa Lopez, Ryan Lowe, Patricia Lue, Anna Makanju, Kim Malfacini, Sam Manning, Todor Markov,
464 Yaniv Markovski, Bianca Martin, Katie Mayer, Andrew Mayne, Bob McGrew, Scott Mayer McKinney,
465 Christine McLeavey, Paul McMillan, Jake McNeil, David Medina, Aalok Mehta, Jacob Menick, Luke
466 Metz, Andrey Mishchenko, Pamela Mishkin, Vinnie Monaco, Evan Morikawa, Daniel Mossing, Tong
467 Mu, Mira Murati, Oleg Murk, David Mély, Ashvin Nair, Reiichiro Nakano, Rajeev Nayak, Arvind Nee-
468 lakantan, Richard Ngo, Hyeonwoo Noh, Long Ouyang, Cullen O’Keefe, Jakub Pachocki, Alex Paino,
469 Joe Palermo, Ashley Pantuliano, Giambattista Parascandolo, Joel Parish, Emy Parparita, Alex Pas-
470 sos, Mikhail Pavlov, Andrew Peng, Adam Perelman, Filipe de Avila Belbute Peres, Michael Petrov,
471 Henrique Ponde de Oliveira Pinto, Michael, Pokorny, Michelle Pokrass, Vitchyr H. Pong, Tolly Powell,
472 Alethea Power, Boris Power, Elizabeth Proehl, Raul Puri, Alec Radford, Jack Rae, Aditya Ramesh,
473 Cameron Raymond, Francis Real, Kendra Rimbach, Carl Ross, Bob Rotsted, Henri Roussez, Nick Ry-
474 der, Mario Saltarelli, Ted Sanders, Shibani Santurkar, Girish Sastry, Heather Schmidt, David Schnurr,
475 John Schulman, Daniel Selsam, Kyla Sheppard, Toki Sherbakov, Jessica Shieh, Sarah Shoker, Pranav
476 Shyam, Szymon Sidor, Eric Sigler, Maddie Simens, Jordan Sitkin, Katarina Slama, Ian Sohl, Benjamin
477 Sokolowsky, Yang Song, Natalie Staudacher, Felipe Petroski Such, Natalie Summers, Ilya Sutskever, Jie

- 478 Tang, Nikolas Tezak, Madeleine B. Thompson, Phil Tillet, Amin Tootoonchian, Elizabeth Tseng, Pre-
479 ston Tuggle, Nick Turley, Jerry Tworek, Juan Felipe Cerón Uribe, Andrea Vallone, Arun Vijayvergiya,
480 Chelsea Voss, Carroll Wainwright, Justin Jay Wang, Alvin Wang, Ben Wang, Jonathan Ward, Ja-
481 son Wei, CJ Weinmann, Akila Welihinda, Peter Welinder, Jiayi Weng, Lilian Weng, Matt Wiethoff,
482 Dave Willner, Clemens Winter, Samuel Wolrich, Hannah Wong, Lauren Workman, Sherwin Wu, Jeff
483 Wu, Michael Wu, Kai Xiao, Tao Xu, Sarah Yoo, Kevin Yu, Qiming Yuan, Wojciech Zaremba, Rowan
484 Zellers, Chong Zhang, Marvin Zhang, Shengjia Zhao, Tianhao Zheng, Juntang Zhuang, William Zhuk,
485 and Barret Zoph. Gpt-4 technical report, 2024. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2303.08774>.
- [2] Albert Q. Jiang, Alexandre Sablayrolles, Arthur Mensch, Chris Bamford, Devendra Singh Chaplot,
486 Diego de las Casas, Florian Bressand, Gianna Lengyel, Guillaume Lample, Lucile Saulnier, Lelio Renard
487 Lavaud, Marie-Anne Lachaux, Pierre Stock, Teven Le Scao, Thibaut Lavril, Thomas Wang, Timothee
488 Lacroix, and William El Sayed. Mistral 7b, 2023. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.06825>.
- [3] AI@Meta. Llama 3 model card. *N.A.*, 2024. URL [https://github.com/meta-llama/llama3/blob/
490 main/MODEL_CARD.md](https://github.com/meta-llama/llama3/blob/main/MODEL_CARD.md).
- [4] DeepSeek-AI, Aixin Liu, Bei Feng, et al. Deepseek-v3 technical report, 2025. URL [https://arxiv.
492 org/abs/2412.19437](https://arxiv.org/abs/2412.19437).
- [5] Elizabeth Clark, Tal August, Sofia Serrano, Nikita Haduong, Suchin Gururangan, and Noah A
493 Smith. All that’s human’s not gold: Evaluating human evaluation of generated text. *arXiv preprint
494 arXiv:2107.00061*, 2021.
- [6] Wenxuan Zhang, Yue Deng, Bing Liu, Sinno Jialin Pan, and Lidong Bing. Sentiment analysis in the
495 era of large language models: A reality check. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2305.15005*, 2023.
- [7] Minxue Niu, Mimansa Jaiswal, and Emily Mower Provost. From text to emotion: Unveiling the emotion
496 annotation capabilities of llms. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2408.17026*, 2024.
- [8] Luis De-Marcos and Adrian Dominguez-Diaz. Llm-based topic modeling for dark web q&a forums: A
497 comparative analysis with traditional methods. *IEEE Access*, 2025.
- [9] Shervin Minaee, Tomas Mikolov, Narjes Nikzad, Meysam Chenaghlu, Richard Socher, Xavier Amatriain,
498 and Jianfeng Gao. Large language models: A survey, 2025. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2402.06196>.
- [10] Yilei Wang, Jiabao Zhao, Deniz S Ones, Liang He, and Xin Xu. Evaluating the ability of large language
499 models to emulate personality. *Scientific reports*, 15(1):519, 2025.
- [11] Edoardo Sebastiano De Duro, Riccardo Improta, and Massimo Stella. Introducing counsellme: A
500 dataset of simulated mental health dialogues for comparing llms like haiku, llamantino and chatgpt
501 against humans. *Emerging Trends in Drugs, Addictions, and Health*, page 100170, 2025.
- [12] Fan Yang, Jie Bai, Linjing Li, and Daniel Zeng. Modeling social opinion evolution with llm agents:
502 Integrating personality traits with embedded opinion dynamics. In *2025 International Joint Conference
503 on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*, pages 1–8. IEEE, 2025.
- [13] Joon Sung Park, Joseph O’Brien, Carrie Jun Cai, Meredith Ringel Morris, Percy Liang, and Michael S
504 Bernstein. Generative agents: Interactive simulacra of human behavior. In *Proceedings of the 36th
505 annual acm symposium on user interface software and technology*, pages 1–22, 2023.
- [14] Joon Sung Park, Carolyn Q. Zou, Aaron Shaw, Benjamin Mako Hill, Carrie Cai, Meredith Ringel
506 Morris, Robb Willer, Percy Liang, and Michael S. Bernstein. Generative agent simulations of 1,000
507 people, 2024. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2411.10109>.
- [15] Amir Taubenfeld, Yaniv Dover, Roi Reichart, and Ariel Goldstein. Systematic biases in llm simulations
508 of debates. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2402.04049*, 2024.

- 521 [16] Yujin Potter, Shiyang Lai, Junsol Kim, James Evans, and Dawn Song. Hidden persuaders: Llms’
522 political leaning and their influence on voters. In *Proceedings of the 2024 Conference on Empirical*
523 *Methods in Natural Language Processing*, pages 4244–4275, 2024.
- 524 [17] Marcel Binz, Elif Akata, Matthias Bethge, Franziska Brändle, Fred Callaway, Julian Coda-Forno, Peter
525 Dayan, Can Demircan, Maria K Eckstein, Noémi Éltető, et al. A foundation model to predict and
526 capture human cognition. *Nature*, pages 1–8, 2025.
- 527 [18] Giulio Rossetti, Massimo Stella, Rémy Cazabet, Katherine Abramski, Erica Cau, Salvatore Citraro,
528 Andrea Failla, Virginia Morini, and Valentina Pansanella. Ysocial: an ai-powered social media virtual
529 twin. *Big Data & Society*, 2026. doi: 10.1177/20539517261431576.
- 530 [19] Ariel Flint Ashery, Luca Maria Aiello, and Andrea Baronchelli. Emergent social conventions and col-
531 lective bias in llm populations. *Science Advances*, 11(20):eadu9368, 2025.
- 532 [20] Stefano Nolfi. On the unexpected abilities of large language models. *Adaptive Behavior*, 32(6):493–502,
533 2024.
- 534 [21] David Premack and Guy Woodruff. Does the chimpanzee have a theory of mind? *Behavioral and*
535 *Brain Sciences*, 1(4):515–526, December 1978. ISSN 1469-1825. doi: 10.1017/s0140525x00076512. URL
536 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X00076512>.
- 537 [22] Zengqing Wu, Run Peng, Takayuki Ito, and Chuan Xiao. Llm-based social simulations require a bound-
538 ary. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2506.19806*, 2025.
- 539 [23] Huao Li, Yu Quan Chong, Simon Stepputtis, Joseph Campbell, Dana Hughes, Michael Lewis, and
540 Katia Sycara. Theory of mind for multi-agent collaboration via large language models. *arXiv preprint*
541 *arXiv:2310.10701*, 2023.
- 542 [24] Maarten Sap, Ronan LeBras, Daniel Fried, and Yejin Choi. Neural theory-of-mind? on the limits of
543 social intelligence in large lms. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2210.13312*, 2022.
- 544 [25] Winnie Street, John Oliver Siy, Geoff Keeling, Adrien Baranes, Benjamin Barnett, Michael McKibben,
545 Tatenda Kanyere, Alison Lentz, Robin IM Dunbar, et al. Llms achieve adult human performance on
546 higher-order theory of mind tasks. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2405.18870*, 2024.
- 547 [26] James WA Strachan, Dalila Albergio, Giulia Borghini, Oriana Pansardi, Eugenio Scaliti, Saurabh Gupta,
548 Krati Saxena, Alessandro Rufo, Stefano Panzeri, Guido Manzi, et al. Testing theory of mind in large
549 language models and humans. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 8(7):1285–1295, 2024.
- 550 [27] Tomer Ullman. Large language models fail on trivial alterations to theory-of-mind tasks. *arXiv preprint*
551 *arXiv:2302.08399*, 2023.
- 552 [28] Michal Kosinski. Evaluating large language models in theory of mind tasks. *Proceedings of the National*
553 *Academy of Sciences*, 121(45):e2405460121, 2024.
- 554 [29] Simon Martin Breum, Daniel Væ dele Egdal, Victor Gram Mortensen, Anders Giovanni Mø ller, and
555 Luca Maria Aiello. The persuasive power of large language models. In *Proceedings of the International*
556 *AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media*, volume 18, pages 152–163, 2024.
- 557 [30] Miller McPherson, Lynn Smith-Lovin, and James M Cook. Birds of a feather: Homophily in social
558 networks. *Annual review of sociology*, 27(1):415–444, 2001.
- 559 [31] Xinnong Zhang, Jiayu Lin, Xinyi Mou, Shiyue Yang, Xiawei Liu, Libo Sun, Hanjia Lyu, Yihang Yang,
560 Weihong Qi, Yue Chen, et al. Socioverse: A world model for social simulation powered by llm agents
561 and a pool of 10 million real-world users. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2504.10157*, 2025.
- 562 [32] Tim Donkers and Jürgen Ziegler. Understanding online polarization through human-agent interaction
563 in a synthetic llm-based social network. *N.A.*, 2025.

- 564 [33] Dorottya Demszky, Diyi Yang, David S Yeager, Christopher J Bryan, Margaret Clapper, Susannah
565 Chandhok, Johannes C Eichstaedt, Cameron Hecht, Jeremy Jamieson, Meghann Johnson, et al. Using
566 large language models in psychology. *Nature Reviews Psychology*, 2(11):688–701, 2023.
- 567 [34] Luca Rossi, Katherine Harrison, and Irina Shklovski. The problems of llm-generated data in social
568 science research. *Sociologica: International Journal for Sociological Debate*, 18(2):145–168, 2024.
- 569 [35] Aliakbar Mehdizadeh and Martin Hilbert. Homophily-induced emergence of biased structures in llm-
570 based multi-agent ai systems. *Social Network Analysis and Mining*, 15(1):1–25, 2025.
- 571 [36] Fariba Karimi, Mathieu Génois, Claudia Wagner, Philipp Singer, and Markus Strohmaier. Homophily
572 influences ranking of minorities in social networks. *Scientific reports*, 8(1):11077, 2018.
- 573 [37] Mrinank Sharma, Meg Tong, Tomasz Korbak, David Duvenaud, Amanda Askeell, Samuel R Bowman,
574 Esin DURMUS, Zac Hatfield-Dodds, Scott R Johnston, Shauna M Kravec, et al. Towards understanding
575 sycophancy in language models. In *The Twelfth International Conference on Learning Representations*,
576 pages 383–390, 2025.
- 577 [38] Erica Cau, Valentina Pansanella, Dino Pedreschi, and Giulio Rossetti. Selective agreement, not syc-
578 ophancy: investigating opinion dynamics in llm interactions. *EPJ Data Science*, 14(1):59, 2025.
- 579 [39] Claudio Castellano, Santo Fortunato, and Vittorio Loreto. Statistical physics of social dynamics. *Reviews*
580 *of modern physics*, 81(2):591, 2009.
- 581 [40] Xia-Meng Si and Chen Li. Bounded confidence opinion dynamics in virtual networks and real networks.
582 *Journal of Computers*, 29(3):220–228, 2018.
- 583 [41] Richard A Holley and Thomas M Liggett. Ergodic theorems for weakly interacting infinite systems and
584 the voter model. *The annals of probability*, pages 643–663, 1975.
- 585 [42] Guillaume Deffuant, David Neau, Frederic Amblard, and Gérard Weisbuch. Mixing beliefs among
586 interacting agents. *Advances in Complex Systems*, 3(01n04):87–98, 2000.
- 587 [43] Paul L Krapivsky and Sidney Redner. Dynamics of majority rule in two-state interacting spin systems.
588 *Physical Review Letters*, 90(23):238701, 2003.
- 589 [44] Irving Crespi. *The public opinion process: How the people speak*. Routledge, 2013.
- 590 [45] Hossein Noorazar. Recent advances in opinion propagation dynamics: A 2020 survey. *The European*
591 *Physical Journal Plus*, 135:1–20, 2020.
- 592 [46] Alina Sîrbu, Vittorio Loreto, Vito DP Servedio, and Francesca Tria. Opinion dynamics: models, ex-
593 tensions and external effects. *Participatory sensing, opinions and collective awareness*, pages 363–401,
594 2017.
- 595 [47] PETER CLIFFORD and AIDAN SUDBURY. A model for spatial conflict. *Biometrika*, 60(3):581–588,
596 1973. ISSN 1464-3510. doi: 10.1093/biomet/60.3.581. URL [http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/biomet/60.](http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/biomet/60.3.581)
597 [3.581](http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/biomet/60.3.581).
- 598 [48] Morris H. Degroot. Reaching a consensus. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 69(345):
599 118–121, March 1974. ISSN 1537-274X. doi: 10.1080/01621459.1974.10480137. URL [http://dx.doi.](http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/01621459.1974.10480137)
600 [org/10.1080/01621459.1974.10480137](http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/01621459.1974.10480137).
- 601 [49] Giordano De Marzo, Luciano Pietronero, and David Garcia. Emergence of scale-free networks in social
602 interactions among large language models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2312.06619*, 2023.
- 603 [50] Chen Gao, Xiaochong Lan, Zhihong Lu, Jinzhu Mao, Jinghua Piao, Huandong Wang, Depeng Jin, and
604 Yong Li. S3: Social-network simulation system with large language model-empowered agents. *arXiv*
605 *preprint arXiv:2307.14984*, 2023.

- 606 [51] Chengxing Xie, Canyu Chen, Feiran Jia, Ziyu Ye, Kai Shu, Adel Bibi, Ziniu Hu, Philip Torr, Bernard
607 Ghanem, and Guohao Li. Can large language model agents simulate human trust behaviors? *arXiv
608 preprint arXiv:2402.04559*, 2024.
- 609 [52] Joon Sung Park, Lindsay Popowski, Carrie Cai, Meredith Ringel Morris, Percy Liang, and Michael S.
610 Bernstein. Social simulacra: Creating populated prototypes for social computing systems. In *Proceedings
611 of the 35th Annual ACM Symposium on User Interface Software and Technology, UIST '22*, pages 383–
612 390, New York, NY, USA, 2022. Association for Computing Machinery. ISBN 9781450393201. doi:
613 10.1145/3526113.3545616. URL <https://doi.org/10.1145/3526113.3545616>.
- 614 [53] Pranav Bhandari, Nicolas Fay, Michael J Wise, Amitava Datta, Stephanie Meek, Usman Naseem, and
615 Mehwish Nasim. Can llm agents maintain a persona in discourse? In *Proceedings of the 2025 Conference
616 on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*, pages 29201–29217, 2025.
- 617 [54] Yun-Shiuan Chuang, Agam Goyal, Nikunj Harlalka, Siddharth Suresh, Robert Hawkins, Sijia Yang,
618 Dhavan Shah, Junjie Hu, and Timothy T Rogers. Simulating opinion dynamics with networks of llm-
619 based agents. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2311.09618*, 2023.
- 620 [55] Fabian Lorig, Emil Johansson, and Paul Davidsson. Agent-based social simulation of the covid-19
621 pandemic: A systematic review. *Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation*, 24(3), 2021.
- 622 [56] Petter Törnberg, Diliara Valeeva, Justus Uitermark, and Christopher Bail. Simulating social media using
623 large language models to evaluate alternative news feed algorithms. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2310.05984*,
624 2023.
- 625 [57] Yun-Shiuan Chuang, Agam Goyal, Nikunj Harlalka, Siddharth Suresh, Robert Hawkins, Sijia Yang,
626 Dhavan Shah, Junjie Hu, and Timothy T. Rogers. Simulating opinion dynamics with networks of
627 llm-based agents, 2024. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2311.09618>.
- 628 [58] Corrado Monti, Luca Maria Aiello, Gianmarco De Francisci Morales, and Francesco Bonchi. The
629 language of opinion change on social media under the lens of communicative action. *Scientific Reports*,
630 12(1):17920, 2022.
- 631 [59] Pedro Cisneros-Velarde. On the principles behind opinion dynamics in multi-agent systems of large
632 language models, 2024. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.15492>.
- 633 [60] David Rozado. The political preferences of llms. *PLOS ONE*, 19, 2024. URL [https://api.
634 semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:267412830](https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:267412830).
- 635 [61] Mirko Farina and Andrea Lavazza. Chatgpt in society: emerging issues. *Frontiers in Artificial Intelli-
636 gence*, 6, 2023. URL <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:259168081>.
- 637 [62] Erica Cau, Andrea Failla, and Giulio Rossetti. Bots of a feather: mixing biases in llms’ opinion dynamics.
638 In *International conference on complex networks and their applications*, pages 166–176. Springer, 2024.
- 639 [63] Brendan Nyhan and Jason Reifler. When corrections fail: The persistence of political misperceptions.
640 *Political Behavior*, 32(2):303–330, 2010.
- 641 [64] J. Dryden and A.H. Clough. *Parallel Lives*. e-artnow, 2018. ISBN 9788027244577. URL [https:
642 //books.google.it/books?id=-amSDwAAQBAJ](https://books.google.it/books?id=-amSDwAAQBAJ).
- 643 [65] Gemma Team, Aishwarya Kamath, Johan Ferret, Shreya Pathak, Nino Vieillard, Ramona Merhej,
644 Sarah Perrin, Tatiana Matejovicova, Alexandre Ramé, Morgane Rivière, et al. Gemma 3 technical
645 report. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2503.19786*, 2025.
- 646 [66] Mehdi Moussaïd, Juliane E Kämmer, Pantelis P Analytis, and Hansjörg Neth. Social influence and the
647 collective dynamics of opinion formation. *PloS one*, 8(11):e78433, 2013.
- 648 [67] Aliakbar Mehdizadeh and Martin Hilbert. When your ai agent succumbs to peer-pressure: Studying
649 opinion-change dynamics of llms. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2510.19107*, 2025.

- 650 [68] Myra Cheng, Sunny Yu, Cino Lee, Pranav Khadpe, Lujain Ibrahim, and Dan Jurafsky. Elephant:
651 Measuring and understanding social sycophancy in llms. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2505.13995*, 2025.
- 652 [69] Aaron Fanous, Jacob Goldberg, Ank Agarwal, Joanna Lin, Anson Zhou, Sonnet Xu, Vasiliki Bikia,
653 Roxana Daneshjou, and Sanmi Koyejo. Syceval: Evaluating llm sycophancy. In *Proceedings of the*
654 *AAAI/ACM Conference on AI, Ethics, and Society*, volume 8, pages 893–900, 2025.
- 655 [70] Sheena Tahira Khan, Vilas Ramrao Joshi, Deepak Bhardwaj, Surender Kumar Sharma, Shaikh Abdul
656 Waheed, and Deepak K Sharma. Mitigating voltage fluctuations in grid-tied pv systems: power qual-
657 ity enhancement. In *2024 3rd International Conference on Computational Modelling, Simulation and*
658 *Optimization (ICCMO)*, pages 407–416. IEEE, 2024.
- 659 [71] Alina Sirbu, Dino Pedreschi, Fosca Giannotti, and János Kertész. Algorithmic bias amplifies opinion
660 fragmentation and polarization: A bounded confidence model. *PloS one*, 14(3):e0213246, 2019.
- 661 [72] Valentina Pansanella, Giulio Rossetti, and Letizia Milli. From mean-field to complex topologies: net-
662 work effects on the algorithmic bias model. In *Complex Networks & Their Applications X: Volume*
663 *2, Proceedings of the Tenth International Conference on Complex Networks and Their Applications*
664 *COMPLEX NETWORKS 2021 10*, pages 329–340. Springer, 2022.
- 665 [73] Albert-László Barabási and Réka Albert. Emergence of scaling in random networks. *science*, 286(5439):
666 509–512, 1999.